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Comparative Effectiveness of Digital Learning Environment and Problem- Based Learning on Students' Achievement in Chemistry

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ABSTRACT

The study explored the comparative effectiveness of digital learning environment and problem-based learning on secondary school students' achievement in chemistry in Taraba State. The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design. The population comprised all the 5361 secondary school one (SS1) students taking chemistry in the Education Zone. The sample size was 150 students from two sampled intact classes and selected using purposive sampling. A total of 70 students were in the experimental group 1 and taught chemistry in a digital learning environment aided by Physics Education Technology (PhET) Package while 80 students were in the experimental group 2 and learned through problem based strategy. Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) was used for data collection. CAT was validated by three experts: two from science education and one from measurement and evaluation unit all from Taraba State University, Jalingo. Reliability index of CAT was found to be 0.83 using Kuder-Richardson 20. Mean and standard deviation and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were used for data analyses. The findings revealed that students taught in a digital learning environment achieved significantly higher than those in problem-based learning ($p < 0.05$). There was no significant effect of gender on achievement ($p > 0.05$). It was concluded that when students learn in a digital environment, their achievement improves. It was recommended among others that teachers should integrate digital learning into chemistry instructions for enhancement of achievement.

Keywords: Digital learning, problem-based learning, achievement, gender, chemistry

INTRODUCTION

Science and technology have long been established as ingredients for national development. It is no coincidence that countries that have robust scientific and technological practices are considered more developed than countries with low scientific and technological practices. To this regards, nations have adopted science teaching in their schools in order to proliferate scientific literacy at all levels. Chemistry, which is one of the major science subjects with its complex concepts and abstract nature, presents particular challenges in teaching and learning. Exploring the effectiveness of different teaching approaches in this subject is crucial in this 21st century.

One of the trademarks of learning in the 21st century is the digitalization of learning. Walker (2024) defined digital learning as one that is supported by technology; it is an umbrella name for all forms of learning involving computers, internet, and mobile phones among others. A classroom or any educational setting where students learn primarily through computers and internet is a digital learning environment. Science is dynamic and so also should its teaching and learning be. The dynamics here entails that since the world is currently in the information age where computers have been inseparable with human activities and endeavours, the teaching and learning of science should tilt to that effect. It was observed in

Walters (2022) that schools have recognized that digitalization is crucial in providing positive learning experiences. Brooks (2022) posited that computer hardware such as interactive whiteboards and software such as gamification are advancement in learning technologies that continue to transform educational landscape. This transformation is commendable as there are different dimension of what a digital learning environment or digital learning constitutes.

Digital learning is quite broad that it cannot be boxed into a single sense. For Walker (2024), digital learning could be anyone of the following: i) Traditional face-to-face learning which is supplemented with technology; ii) Use of online information sources; including databases, and information gained though personal study and research; iii) Blended learning; where there is a mix of traditional and computer based learning ; iv) Mobile learning; where learning is completed using a mobile phone; and v) Education delivered via computer, mobile phone, or Internet accessible device. Walters (2022) summarized the benefits of digital learning to include full-time access to materials, facilitates collaboration, more resources, and better engagement, personalized learning, facilitates new digital learning strategies, and preparation for work building peer communities. Apparently, digital learning has become a prerequisite factor for acquiring knowledge (Fareen, 2022). One pedagogical advantage of digital learning environment is that they can readily combine with other instructional strategies to make learning more effective. For the purpose of this study, the Physics Education Technology (PhET) interactive simulation was considered for the digital learning environment.

PhET interactive simulation belongs to the class of education delivered via computer, mobile phone or internet accessible device. Interactive computer simulations offer interactive and appealing interfaces with functions of repeated manipulations and observations (Banda & Nzabahimana, 2023). PhET simulations are research-based, highly interactive, animated, and easy to use interactive digital environment and they create a game-like environment which models real-life scenarios, and do not need many computer specifications (Banda & Nzabahimana, 2023). PhET Interactive Simulations are dynamic, interactive tools created by the University of Colorado Boulder to facilitate the learning of science and mathematics through exploration and discovery. These simulations are available for practical exploration across various scientific disciplines, including biology, chemistry, physics, and mathematics. They provide an engaging digital environment where users can manipulate variables, visualize processes, and conduct experiments. It is available and accessible online at phet.colorado.edu, PhET simulations are free to use, though they require an internet connection and a device with a relatively large screen for optimal usability. PhET simulation has been ranked in Tsai (2024) as one of the top 15 best digital experimentation platforms since it offer interactive, virtual environments for exploring chemical concepts. In chemistry education, PhET simulations provide a visual and interactive platform for students to explore complex chemical concepts, potentially making them more engaging and easier to understand. They offer a virtual laboratory experience, allowing students to conduct experiments and manipulate variables without the limitations of physical lab equipment or safety concerns. They can also help students visualize abstract concepts, such as molecular interactions or chemical reactions, which can be challenging to grasp through traditional teaching methods. Research (Sam & Stephen, 2025) suggests that PhET simulations can lead to improved understanding of specific chemistry concepts and enhanced science process skills. Some studies (Sam & Stephen, 2025) suggest that while PhET simulations can benefit all students, there might be subtle differences in how boys and girls engage with and learn from them.

More so, another instruction strategy Problem-Based Learning (PBL) in chemistry which uses student-centered approach encourages active learning and critical thinking by presenting students with real-world problems that they need to solve through research and collaboration. It emphasizes the application of learned concepts to solve practical problems, promoting deeper understanding and retention of knowledge. Development of 21st-Century skills fosters the development of essential 21st- century skills like problem-solving, critical thinking, communication, and teamwork. According to Budiman et al. as cited in Susilawati and Doyan (2023), PBL is a classroom learning model that in the classroom learning activities, there are real problems used as a reference for students to be able to think creatively and critically in order to find solutions to problems given by the teacher. Imaniah et al. (2023) viewed it as a

learning concept that helps educators build a learning environment that begins with important and relevant issues for students to enable them obtain a more real-life learning experience. Essentially, in this strategy, problem drives learning. Problems are posed or presented such that the solving process instills content knowledge and higher order thinking skills in the learners. These higher order thinking skills are important in science and chemistry particularly as chemistry has a wide range of real life applications. The choice of problem-based learning as an instructional strategy is guided by Anyawu (2020) who believed that educators must create learning environments that foster the acquisition of scientific and technical skills, catering to all learners' diverse needs and interests. As such, PBL could serve as such a learning environment that caters for learners' different learning needs and styles. A problem exists once someone has a goal but does not know how to achieve it (Gunawan et al, 2019). Sitorus et al. (2016) posited five steps involved in resolution of problems in this strategy: i. Definition of problem, ii. Problem diagnosis, iii. Formulation of alternative strategies, iv. Implementation of strategies of choice, and v. Evaluation of the process and result. When teachers painstakingly implement this strategy, students' achievement and higher order skills will receive a boost.

Hence, this research background lies in the growing interest in innovative teaching methods, particularly digital and problem-based learning, and their potential to enhance student achievement in subjects like Chemistry. This study explores the comparative effectiveness of digital (PhET simulations) and problem-based learning (PBL) in teaching chemistry, with a particular focus on how these methods influence student achievement and potentially differ based on gender. Understanding the impact of these methods, and whether they affect students differently based on their gender, is crucial for optimizing chemistry education. Studies (Ajayi & Oladele, 2024; Sam & Stephen, 2025) comparing PhET simulations and PBL separately in chemistry education have yielded mixed results. Some studies show that PhET simulations can be more effective for certain topics or for students with specific learning styles. There is evidence suggesting that both PhET simulations (Sam & Stephen, 2025) and PBL (Ajayi & Oladele, 2024) can be beneficial for both male and female students, but the specific learning outcomes and engagement levels might differ. Hence, more research is needed to understand the specific ways in which PhET simulations and PBL impact student achievement in chemistry, and whether these impacts vary based on gender most especially in Taraba State where exists a gap in literatures. Understanding the potential gender differences can help educators tailor their teaching methods to maximize the effectiveness of both PhET simulations and PBL for all students. And, the effectiveness of each method, and how it interacts with gender, requires further investigation. A balanced approach that integrates both methods, while considering individual learning styles and preferences, might be the most effective way to optimize student learning in chemistry.

The primary problem addressed in this study is the need to compare the effectiveness of digital learning and problem-based learning in promoting student achievement in chemistry where gaps exists. While there's evidence suggesting the positive impact of both digital and problem-based learning, research findings on their comparative effectiveness may be mixed or limited. However, none of the previous efforts in Taraba State have compared the effectiveness of these two strategies on students' achievement, with a focus on potential gender differences. And, with the pressing need to replace traditional methods, there is need to compare strategies to obtain evidence on which is more effective. Hence, a rigorous comparative study is needed to provide empirical evidence on which method is more effective in promoting student achievement in chemistry. Consequently, the study sought to answer the question: 'Which will improve students' achievement: Learning in digital environment or using problem-based learning; and any gender difference in both strategies?' It is in light of this and the foregoing that this study investigated the comparative effectiveness of digital (PhET simulation) and problem-based learning on achievement among secondary school students in chemistry in Taraba State.

Purpose of the Study

The specific objectives of the study were to determine;

1. Achievement of students taught chemistry concepts through digital learning environment and students taught using problem based learning.

2. Achievement of male and female students taught chemistry concepts through digital learning environment.
3. Achievement of male and female students taught chemistry concepts through problem based learning.

Research Questions

The study answered the following questions; what is the

1. Mean achievement score of students taught chemistry concepts through digital learning environment and students taught using problem based learning.
2. Mean achievement score of male and female students taught chemistry concepts through digital learning environment.
3. Mean achievement score of male and female students taught chemistry concepts through problem based learning.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H0₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of students taught chemistry concepts through digital learning environment and students taught using problem based learning.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of male and female students taught chemistry concepts through digital learning environment.

H0₃: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of male and female students taught chemistry concepts through problem based learning.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design of pre-test, post-test non-equivalent groups. The research design was considered appropriate because the study seeks to infer cause-and-effect relationship using non-random criteria of intact classes. The population comprised all the 5361 secondary school one (SS 1) students taking chemistry in the Education Zone.

The sample size was 150 students from the two sampled intact classes. Purposive sampling was used to select two intact classes while random sampling was used to assign the classes into experimental group 1 and 2 with the criteria being the availability of functional computers with which the digital learning was conducted.

A total of 70 students were in the experimental group 1 and taught chemistry in a digital learning environment aided by Physics Education Technology (PhET) Package while 80 students were in the experimental group 2 and learned through problem based strategy. The PhET simulations used for this study provided a visual and interactive platform for students to explore complex chemical concepts, potentially making them more engaging and easier to understand. It offered a virtual laboratory experience, allowing students to conduct experiments and manipulate variables without the limitations of physical lab equipment or safety concerns. It also helped the students visualize abstract concepts through active exploration of the stipulated PhET sim on topics taught using the inclusive features and provide access to wider range of resources. While, the PBL encouraged active learning and critical thinking by presenting students with real-world problems that they need to solve through research and collaboration on the topics Boyle's and Charles' law and balancing chemical equations. It emphasized the application of learned concepts to solve practical problems, promoting deeper understanding and retention of knowledge. It also fostered the development of essential skills like problem-solving, critical thinking, communication, and teamwork.

A 35-item Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) was used for data collection. The items were adapted from past external examination questions on the topics Boyle's and Charles' law and balancing chemical equations. CAT was validated by three experts: two from science education and one from measurement and evaluation unit all from Taraba State University, Jalingo. Reliability indices of CAT was found to be 0.83 using Kuder Richardson 20 formula following a pilot test with 35 students outside the scope of the study. Mean and standard deviation and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were used for data analyses.

RESULTS

The results are presented in Tables 1-6 to answer the research questions/test the hypotheses.

Research Question 1: *What is the mean achievement score of students taught chemistry concepts through digital learning environment and students taught using problem based learning?*

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of achievement score between students exposed to digital learning environment and problem based learning

Group		PreCAT	PostCAT	Mean gain
DLE	Mean	10.07	27.83	17.76
	N	70	70	
	Std. Deviation	2.90	1.88	
PBL	Mean	10.51	24.59	14.08
	N	80	80	
	Std. Deviation	3.38	2.03	
Mean difference		0.44	3.24	3.68

Table 1 indicates that before treatment, students in the digital learning group, being the experimental group 1, had mean achievement score of 10.07 with standard deviation of 2.90 while students in the experimental group 2 exposed to problem based learning had a mean of 10.51 with standard deviation of 3.38. This means that initially, students in the problem based learning performed slightly better than students in the digital learning group with mean difference of 0.44. The standard deviation values at this stage depict that the scores of students in the problem based learning group were more dispersed compared to students in the digital learning group since it had a higher standard deviation (3.38 to 2.90). After treatment exercise, students in the digital learning environment group had a mean achievement score of 27.83 with standard deviation of 1.88 while students in the problem based learning group had mean achievement score of 24.59 with standard deviation of 2.03. The standard deviation values at this stage depict that the scores of students in the problem based learning group were more dispersed compared to students in the digital learning group since it had a higher standard deviation (2.03 to 1.88). Apparently, students in the digital learning group performed better than their counterparts in problem based group as they gained 17.76 to 14.08 obtained by students in the problem based learning group. The difference in mean gain is 3.68 in favour of digital learning environment group.

Research Question 2: *What is the mean achievement score of male and female students taught chemistry concepts through digital learning environment?*

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of achievement score of male and female students exposed to digital learning environment

Gender DLE		preCAT	PostCAT	mean gain
Male	Mean	9.77	28.10	18.33
	N	31	31	
	Std. Deviation	2.81	1.89	
Female	Mean	10.31	27.62	17.31
	N	39	39	
	Std. Deviation	2.98	1.87	
Mean difference		0.54	0.48	1.02

Table 2 indicates that at pre-test, male students in the digital learning group had mean achievement score of 9.77 with standard deviation of 2.81 while their female counterparts had a mean of 10.31 with standard deviation of 2.98. This means that initially, the female students performed slightly better than male students in the digital learning group with mean difference of 0.54. The standard deviation values at this stage depict that the scores of female students were more dispersed compared to the male students' scores since it had a higher standard deviation (2.81 to 2.98). After the exercise, male students in the digital

learning environment group had a mean achievement score of 27.10 with standard deviation of 1.89 while female students in the same group had mean achievement score of 27.62 with standard deviation of 1.87. The standard deviation values at this stage depict that the scores of male students in this group were only slightly more dispersed compared to female students in the digital learning group since it had a higher standard deviation (1.89 to 1.87). Apparently, male students appeared to benefit slightly more in terms of achievement than their female counterparts as they gained 18.33 to 17.31 obtained by female students. The difference in mean gain is 1.02 in favour of the male students in the digital learning group.

Research Question 3: *What is the mean achievement score of male and female students taught chemistry concepts through digital learning environment?*

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of achievement score of male and female students exposed to problem based learning

Gender PBL		preCAT	PostCAT	mean gain
Male	Mean	9.71	24.32	14.61
	N	38	38	
	Std. Deviation	3.25	2.00	
Female	Mean	11.24	24.83	13.59
	N	42	42	
	Std. Deviation	3.37	2.05	
Mean difference		1.53	0.51	1.02

Table 3 indicates that at pre-test, male students in the problem based learning group had mean achievement score of 9.71 with standard deviation of 3.25 while their female counterparts had a mean of 11.24 with standard deviation of 3.37. This means that initially, the female students achieved more than male students in the problem based learning group with mean difference of 1.53. The standard deviation values at this stage depict that the scores of female students were more dispersed compared to the male students' scores since it had a higher standard deviation (3.37 to 3.25). After the exercise, male students in the problem based learning group had a mean achievement score of 24.32 with standard deviation of 2.00 while female students in the same group had mean achievement score of 24.83 with standard deviation of 2.05. The standard deviation values at this stage depict that again, the scores of female students in this group were more dispersed compared to female students in the problem based learning group since it had a higher standard deviation (2.05 to 2.00). Apparently, male students appeared to benefit more in terms of achievement than their female counterparts as they gained 14.61 to 13.59 obtained by female students. The difference in mean gain is 1.02 in favour of the male students in the digital learning group.

Testing Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of students taught chemistry concepts through digital learning environment and students taught using problem based learning.

Table 4: ANCOVA statistics of the difference in achievement between students exposed to digital learning environment and problem based learning

Source	Type Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	392.707a	2	196.354	50.746	.000	.408
Intercept	8922.071	1	8922.071	2305.838	.000	.940
PreCAT	.538	1	.538	.139	.710	0.01
Groups	388.238	1	388.238	100.337	.000	.406
Error	568.793	147	3.869			
Total	103143.000	150				
Corrected Total	961.500	149				

Table 4 shows that $F(1,147) = 100.337$ and $p = 0.000$ which is less than the benchmark 0.05. This means that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement of students exposed to digital learning environment and problem based learning. Consequently, null hypothesis 1 is rejected. Research question 1 from table 1 indicated that students in the digital learning group gained more in achievement. Subsequently, this test of hypothesis proves that the difference is statistically significant in favour of digital learning environment. Meaning that digital learning improved students' achievement in chemistry significantly more than problem based learning. In addition, the partial eta squared value of 0.406 shows that about 41% of the variation of the students' achievement in chemistry is accounted for by the effect of the treatment exercise.

Testing Hypothesis 2

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of male and female students taught chemistry concepts through digital learning environment.

Table 5: ANCOVA result of achievement scores of male and female students taught using digital learning environment

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	5.340a	2	2.670	.750	.476	.022
Intercept	4222.899	1	4222.899	1185.798	.000	.947
DLEpreCAT	1.338	1	1.338	.376	.542	.006
DLEgender	3.555	1	3.555	.998	.321	.015
Error	238.602	67	3.561			
Total	54454.000	70				
Corrected Total	243.943	69				

Table 5 shows that $F(1,67) = 0.998$ and $p = 0.321 > 0.05$. This means that the significance level is higher than the benchmark of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis is accepted as this signifies that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of male and female students exposed to digital learning environment. Table 2 showed the mean difference in achievement of male and female students in the digital learning environment where male students gained more in achievement than their female counterparts. However, the result of the test of hypothesis presented in table 8 above shows that the difference is not significant. This means that male and female students taught chemistry through digital learning environment will gain equally in terms of achievement. The partial eta squared value to this regards is 0.015 meaning only about 1.5% of the variation of students' achievement in digital learning environment group was due to gender differences.

Testing Hypothesis 3

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of male and female students taught chemistry concepts through problem based learning

Table 6: ANCOVA result of achievement scores of male and female students taught using problem based learning

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	5.508a	2	2.754	.663	.518	0.17
Intercept	4349.606	1	4349.606	1047.017	.000	.931
PBLpreCAT	.164	1	.164	.039	.843	.001
PBLgender	5.491	1	5.491	1.322	.254	.017
Error	319.880	77	4.154			
Total	48689.000	80				
Corrected Total	325.388	79				

Table 6 shows that $F(1,77) = 1.322$ and $p = 0.254 > 0.05$. This means that the significance level is higher than the benchmark of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis is accepted as this signifies that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of male and female students exposed to problem based learning. Table 3 showed the mean difference in achievement of male and female students in the problem based learning where male students gained more in achievement than their female counterparts. However, the result of the test of hypothesis presented in table 9 above shows that the difference is not significant. This means that male and female students taught chemistry through problem based learning will gain equally in terms of achievement. The partial eta squared value to this regards is 0.017 meaning only about 1.7% of the variation of students' achievement in digital learning environment group was due to gender differences.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The key findings are:

1. There is a significant difference in the mean achievement score of students taught chemistry concepts through digital learning environment and students taught using problem-based learning, in favour of digital learning environment that used PhET simulations.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of male and female students taught chemistry concepts through digital learning environment.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of male and female students taught chemistry concepts through problem-based learning.

The first finding revealed that students in the experimental group 1 who learnt in a digital environment significantly achieved better than their counterparts in the experimental group 2 who learnt using problem based strategy. The digital environment used provided students with opportunities to learn with multiple senses. They could see objects in addition to auditory learning that accompanies it. With the strategy chemical concepts at the molecular and micro molecular levels were better represented. This could be responsible for the significant increase in students' achievement in chemistry. The study aligns with studies that have established the effectiveness of digital learning environment and related terms. The study supports that of Sam and Stephen (2025) who revealed a significant difference in the academic performance in physics by students taught with PhET simulation. The study agrees with Yesgart (2023) who found that students who learned chemistry through technology instructions significantly achieved better with positive impacts than those who learned without the backing of technology. It also aligns with Abraham et al. (2023) who found that use of Google classroom in teaching significantly improved students' achievement relative to conventional strategy of teaching. The finding is also in line with the study of Obodo et al. (2021) who observed that the achievement of students in who learned using digital technology was significantly higher than that of students in the conventional strategy of instruction without technology. The study disagrees with Jack (2023) who found that there is no significant difference in the achievement of students who did computer simulation and students who learned using problem based learning. It also disagrees with Bukari and Asiedu-Addo (2019) who found that problem based learning significantly enhanced students' achievement. There is a reason why technology constantly finds application in the domains of teaching and learning and this effectiveness displayed could catalyze its incorporation into classroom activities.

The second finding with regards to achievement of students between male and female, it was observed that no significant difference existed in the achievement of male and female students exposed to digital learning environment. This infers that digital learning environment takes cognizance of the learning needs of male and female students without favoring one over the other. It has components that both male and female students can conveniently utilize in learning. The finding is consistent with the findings of Sam and Stephen, (2025) in Akwa Ibom State who found that there was no significant difference in the performance of male and female physics students taught wit PhET simulation. It also agrees with Yesgart (2023) who found no statistical significant difference between male and female students who learn through technology enhanced methods. It further conform to the study by Okwuduba et al. (2018) where

it was found therein that no significant difference exists between male and female students achievement in chemistry upon learning through computer simulation strategy which is synonymous to digital learning environment. The finding, however, disagrees with Liwhuliwhue et al. (2023) and Udodi et al. (2023) who found that there is a significant difference in achievement in favour of female and male students respectively in a digital learning class.

The third finding of the study revealed that no significant difference exists in the achievement of male and female students who learned in the problem based learning group. This affirms the gender insensitivity of PBL. It corroborates the finding of Ajayi and Oladele (2024) who observed that male and female students did not show statistically significant difference in achievement when taught using PBL. The finding is in consistent with Oladejo et al. (2021) who revealed that computer simulation helped bridge the gap on gender difference in students' performance in chemistry. The finding further agrees with Bukari and Asiedu-Addo (2019) who found that gender is not a statistically significant factor influencing students' achievement using PBL.

Though, the students that used the digital learning environment (PhET simulations) achieved higher than those students taught with PBL; PhET simulations and PBL can be used as complementary approaches to enhance chemistry learning. PhET simulations can provide a virtual environment for exploring the underlying principles of problems encountered in PBL. The effectiveness of each approach may depend on individual learning styles and preferences (individual needs). Some students may thrive in the interactive, visual environment of PhET simulations, while others may prefer the collaborative and problem-solving focus of PBL.

CONCLUSION/ RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study concluded that when students learn in a digital environment (mostly using PhET simulations), their achievement is greatly enhanced especially in comparison with students who learnt without the backing of digital technology. Similarly, irrespective of whether the learner is a male or female, upon exposure to learning through digital means, the students' achievement will be improved greatly with no gender difference. In conclusion, both PhET simulations and PBL hold promise for improving chemistry education; because these strategies can be effective for all students, understanding the gender-specific influences and optimizing the integration of these approaches is crucial for maximizing their impact on student learning.

The following recommendations have been made in line with what the study revealed:

1. Chemistry teachers in Taraba State should consider the use of digital learning environment such as PhET simulation in teaching students in order to improve achievement. They should be guided on how to effectively use digital learning environment through skill training.
2. Chemistry teachers and school administrators are encouraged to provide male and female students (inclusive) with opportunity to learn through digital environment in order to promote their achievement.
3. PhET simulations and PBL can be used as complementary approaches to enhance chemistry learning. PhET simulations can provide a virtual environment for exploring the underlying principles of problems encountered in PBL. Also, more research is needed to determine the optimal combination of PhET Sims and PBL for different student populations and learning contexts, and more socio-demographic variables.

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